

Baari : A Peek Inside Traditional Multi-Layered Home Gardens of Assam

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Traditional home gardens popularly known as Baari, is an essential part of the socio-economic life of the people of Assam. Currently the home gardens have evolved to a multi-tier, multi-species agricultural that integrates various components of a livelihood. The multi tier characteristics of a home garden is very specific to the household need and selection of varieties depends upon the food habits and choices of the native area as well as the household as most of the produce is for self subsistence, hence selection of multiple plant varieties is based on functional priorities and proper utilization of the available land. People try to utilize every inch of space, from pots on patios to sprawling fields, ensuring a self-sufficient harvest that caters to their immediate needs. Our study has been done by taking a total of 30 home gardens from the area of Pasonisuk gaon, Kaliabor. The aim of our study is to understand the diversification of the species used, their cropping patterns and the utilization of the given space to better reap the benefits of this sustainable source whether through food and nutritional security or by economic means.